

their restoration and inheritance patterns during 1992-93 rabi season (Sep-Jan). All were found to be effective restorers and inherited digenically.

To determine the relationship among the genes, these five testers were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals. The F₁ generation of 10 R × R combinations was raised along with cytoplasmic male sterile line V20 A; A × (R × R) crosses were made. These

10 test cross F₁ progenies (A × (R × R)) were raised at 20- × 19-cm spacing during 1993 kharif season (Jun-Sep). Each combination had 10 rows with 20 plants per row. Their pollen and spikelet fertilities were scored (see table).

The restorer lines differed in their gene action. The test cross progenies from T₁ × T₃, T₁ × T₅, T₃ × T₅, and T₂ × T₄ did not yield any sterile progeny. These lines have identical R alleles

between them while remaining crosses showed segregation, indicating the alleles differed among their parents. These results suggest that the five restorer lines can be divided into group 1 = T₁, T₃, and T₅ and group 2 = T₂ and T₄, which possess different pairs of R genes. A suitable combination of any two of the pairs seems to restore fertility in male sterile lines. ■

Breeding methods

Identifying restorers and maintainers for five cytoplasmic male sterile lines

F. U. Zaman, M. J. Abraham, A. R. Sadananda, F. Mohammad, and Y. Raj, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

Two new cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, Pusa 3 A and Pusa 5 A, were developed. Pusa 3 A has in its background high-yielding Basmati variety Pusa Basmati 1. Pusa 5 A has the aromatic, non-Basmati line Pusa 150. These lines, along with IR58025A, PMS2 A, and PMS3 A, which possess CMS wild abortive cytoplasm, were used to make test crosses. During the 1994 wet season, 326 hybrids and their respective parents were evaluated to identify effective restorers and maintainers for the CMS lines. Each genotype was transplanted in 3-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Standard agronomic practices were followed.

Five plants from each genotype were randomly selected and used for analyzing pollen and spikelet fertility. Anthers from upper, middle, and lower portions

Restorers and maintainers for five CMS lines. New Delhi, India. 1994.

CMS line	Restorers (no.)	Restorers	Maintainers (no.)	Maintainers
IR58025 A	36	PRR3, PRR5, PRR7, PRR8, PRR11, PRR12, PRR16, PRR22, PRR23, PRR25, PRR34, PRR35, PRR38, PRR42, PRR43, PRR44, PRR74, PRR79, PRR82, PRR98, PRR99, PRR100, PRR101, PRR102, PRR103, PRR104, PRR105, PRR107, PRR112, PRR113, PRR114, PRR115, PRR116, PRR117, PRR118, PRR119	7	TC7-2-1-92-39, TC11-3, TC23, TC25-41, P615-K-61, P615-K-271, P615-4-1
PMS3 A	13	PRR2, PRR8, PRR10, PRR24, PRR33, PRR45, PRR47, PRR55, PRR83, PRR84, PRR85, PRR87, PRR89	4	P615-K-160, RCPL 1-87-4, PP94-429, PP94-432
PMS2 A	4	PRR3, PRR5, PRR44, PRR85	3	ADT2008-2-7-1, P1191-3, P1192-2
Pusa 3 A	6	PRR69 ^a , PRR70 ^a , PRR71 ^a , PRR90, PRR94, PRR95	5	TC4-721, TC7-3-1, TCII-7-3-4-1, TC120, HKR91-410
Pusa 5 A	2	PRR57, PRR91	2	P615-K-61, P615-K-172
Total	61		21	

^a = Basmati restorers.

of half emerged panicles were collected and squashed in 2.2% I-KI stain to observe pollen fertility. Cultivars with up to 1% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as perfect maintainers, those with 60-100% pollen and 80-100% spikelet fertility as potential restorers, and the rest as partial restorers.

Three potential Basmati restorers were identified for Pusa 3 A. The frequency of restorers (19%) was higher than that of maintainers (6%) (see table).

We are using the potential restorers to develop new hybrids with improved quality characteristics. Some perfect maintainers with good agronomic traits are being converted into new CMS lines. ■

Androgenesis in rice breeding

N. Mandal, Chinsurah Rice Research Centre, Hooghly 71 21 02, India; S. Sinha and S. Gupta, Botany Department, Bose Institute, Calcutta 700009, India

Plant regeneration efficiency from anther culture of F₁ cross Pankaj × *O. rufipogon* has been improved using He2 + NAA + Kin 0.5 + ABA 2 mg/liter + 5% maltose as

the callus induction medium (see table). Our objective was to transfer the submergence tolerance from the wild species *O. rufipogon* Griff. to the *O. sativa* variety Pankaj.

We used modified MS (NAA 0.5 + Kin 2 mg/liter + 3% sucrose) medium for plant regeneration. Several chlorophyll-deficient plants (albino, xantha, viridis, albo-viridis, virido-albina, virido-xantha,

and striata) and green plants that have different ploidy numbers were obtained. Among the regenerated plants, 73.3% were double haploids. These lines were grown in the field, where 74.8% survived. We examined 696 androgenic lines for different qualitative and quantitative characters. Statistical analysis revealed that the characters within one line were relatively uniform and stably heritable. Among

Effect of basal medium and other supplements on androgenesis of rice.^a

Treatment ^a	Basal medium	Callus induction (%)			Plant regeneration efficiency (%)
		Callus induction (%)	Calli giving green plants ^b (%)	Callus induction (%)	
A	N6	6.8	7.9	53.7	
	He32	8.5	10.8	91.8	
B	N6	6.4	9.5	60.8	
	He2	8.3	13.0	107.9	

^a A = Basal medium + NAA + Kin 0.5 mg/liter + 5% sucrose. B = Basal medium + NAA + Kin 0.5 + ABA 2 mg/liter + 5% maltose. ^b Calli were regenerated on MS + NAA 0.5 + Kin 2 mg/liter + 3% sucrose.

different lines, broad genetic recombinations occurred.

In the next season, 4-wk-old seedlings from each line were submerged in a glasshouse tank for 8 d to select submergence-tolerant types. Starch from the internodes rapidly disappeared upon submergence. The decrease in starch content coincided with a marked increase in amyolytic activity (21.4 EU). Plants

surviving after another 10 d of submergence were recorded. Compared with Pankaj, only PR324 is a high-yielding (4.0-4.4 t/ha), submergence-tolerant type with a lower rate of photorespiration ($P = 0.01$) and wide adaptability. Grain quality is high: protein, 8.6%; amylose, 14.1%; milling percentage, 73%; and length:breadth, 3.5. ■

Using colored-leaf mutants of thermosensitive genic male sterile rice

Shu Qingyao, Xia Yingwu, and Liu Quifu, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029, People's Republic of China

We set up a marker-assisted system to eliminate seed contamination that results from incomplete male sterility of thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines in a two-line hybrid seed production system (see figure). Chlorophyll-deficient leaves (chlorina, albino) were used as markers to determine the

plants to be discarded at the seedling stage. To test the effectiveness of this system, colored-leaf mutants were induced directly in TGMS line 2177S.

In July 1991, dry seeds (13% water content) of 2177S were treated with ⁶⁰Co gamma rays at a dose of 300 Gy. They were sown, transplanted, and grown to maturity. A few seeds of each M₁ plant were harvested to make M₂ progenies. Various non-green seedlings were detected and isolated from these progenies; only a few grew to maturity.

Thirteen heritable colored-leaf mutation lines (M6-7) were developed through successive selection and identifi-

Leaf color transition and morphoagronomic characters of the mutants and 2177S.

Group	Mutant	Leaf color of			Morphoagronomic characters					
		Seedling		Plant	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Growth duration (d)
		20°C	30°C							
I	W3	Cream	Yellowish	Yellow	79.0	19.8	102.7	55.9	27.8	138
	W5	Cream	Yellowish	Yellow	83.8	21.9	109.2	61.3	27.2	141
	W11	Cream	Yellowish	Yellow	74.9	20.2	97.2	50.3	26.0	127
	W12	Cream	Yellowish	Yellow	76.1	18.8	82.2	58.1	27.7	125
	W18	Yellowish	Yellow	Yellow	67.4	18.3	71.7	53.5	26.4	117
II	W1	Albinotic	Yellowish	Green	79.0	19.8	77.5	58.6	25.9	126
	W17	Albinotic	Yellowish	Green	79.3	19.6	91.6	51.7	27.2	123
	W4	Yellow	Albinotic	Green	76.6	20.4	101.8	44.8	27.6	121
	W24	Albinotic	Albinotic	Green	76.5	18.9	87.8	58.9	27.0	121
	W25	Albinotic	Albinotic	Green	74.8	19.6	111.2	46.4	26.1	122
	W27	Albinotic	Albinotic	Green	76.3	20.0	105.2		27.0	122
	W29	Yellow	Yellow	Green	63.8	17.3	64.6	58.4	24.5	123
	W33	Yellow	Yellow	Green	65.5	17.7	66.8	33.4	25.5	126
Check	2177S	Green	Green	Green	75.3	19.3	84.4	47.1	27.0	120

Scheme for eliminating contaminated seed in hybrid rice derived from colored-leaf TGMS lines.

cation. Mutation lines were grouped according to their color transition during growth (see table).

Group I included five yellow-leafed mutants, for which leaves remain yellow or yellowish from seedling to maturity stages. Group II had eight yellow- or albinotic-leafed mutants in which the first 3-4 seedling leaves are albinotic or yellow before the 4th or 5th leaf extends, then the leaves turn greenish while in the seed bed, and finally a normal green at maturity (see table).

All of the F₁ plants had normal green leaves when the mutants were crossed with 2177S or any other variety with normal leaves, suggesting that a recessive gene(s) controls all of the mutations. The leaf color segregation ratio of normal green to mutated color in each F₁ population between the mutants and 2177S was fitted well to a 3-1 ratio, indicating that a single recessive gene controlled all these mutations. Allelic tests of these mutation lines showed that W1 and W17 were controlled by an allelic gene, and so were W3, W5, and W11. Nine nonallelic loci are involved with the 13 mutation lines.

The mutant lines and 2177S were crossed with the conventional line TEC. The morphoagronomic characters of these F₁ plants were recorded and analyzed. No significant differences were detected among them for plant height, panicles per plant, panicle length, grains per panicle, and yield per plant ($P = 0.05$) (data not shown). This suggests that these colored-leaf mutants can be used as markers for eliminating seed contamination in two-line hybrid rice. ■